

THE IMPORTANCE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN THE TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY

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Abstract: *The article mainly discusses the importance of foreign languages in the development and improvement of tourism and hospitality. Because in recent years, that is, before the quarantine, the tourism and hospitality industry has been one of the most profitable types of activity. Many studies show that the knowledge of foreign languages of employees plays a huge role in the development of this activity. It is considered necessary for employees working in this field to know at least 2 other languages besides the local language. Knowing more than one language will give this employee a great advantage and it will be easy to work with guests from many countries.*

Keywords: *tourism, hospitality, language, culture, staff, economy, pedagogy.*

INTRODUCTION

We know that tourism is an international or local income generating activity. In recent years, tourism activity has become a source of high level of income in the economy of many developing and developed countries. Therefore, many countries are paying great attention to the development of tourism and hospitality industry in their regions. Cultural exchange is also taking place in many countries through the development of tourism and hospitality.

At the moment, tourism is becoming one of the most significant macroeconomic sectors and contributing more and more to the global economy each year. As a source of income, this industry plays a significant role in the national economies of many nations across the world.

Due to the world's accelerating processes of globalization, nations must now create an opportunity for the growth of their tourism networks in order to address pressing problems. The growth of the tourism industry was identified as one of the most pressing tasks among them, making it one of the key orientations of the changes being carried out in our nation.

V. Jackmo coined the word "tourism" for the first time in 1830. French speakers use this idea to refer to travel or "tour." Further, it is incorrect to equate the terms "tourist" and "tourism" together. A field made up of all tourist services, tourism is one

of the most significant economic sectors overall. A tourist is a person who engages in this industry and uses a variety of services in his home country or in another place, region, or nation without being compensated. People who travel are considered tourists.

There are already more than a hundred different forms of tourism, and more could develop in the future. As a result, their classification and grouping are crucial challenges. Tourist activity is categorized into types, categories, types, and forms in accordance with its taxonomic basis [1].

Today, there is no question about the tourism industry's impact on the global order and the policies of a number of states and areas. With investment efficiency on par with the oil and gas and automotive industries, tourism has emerged as one of the most lucrative commercial sectors. The interests of the economy, culture, international relations, hotel industry, employment, and transportation organizations are strongly entwined with those of the tourism industry. The growth of tourism is important for both the nation and the person [2].

In order to implement a systematic approach in professional training, a number of issues must be resolved in stages, including the creation of conceptual frameworks, a scientific and methodological foundation, scientific work schedules, and the provision of students with qualified scientific guidance. It should be mentioned that scientific work plays a crucial role in a competitive specialist's professional development, making it one of the top priorities in higher education. All of the bachelor's degree program's components—educational, research, and research work—combine in this way to form a complicated, interrelated process, the outcome of which is based on the use of a systematic approach during the process of organizing it [3].

MAIN PART

The distinguishing feature of using a systematic approach is to identify levels and criteria for judging the professional readiness of tourism bachelors. This is done by establishing goals and objectives, developing a concept for preparing bachelors in the direction of tourism for professional activities, highlighting the structural components of this system, and establishing the relationship between them. Thus, when analyzing any object or phenomena, it is possible to identify external connections and identify the components that bring them together using a systematic methodology. It is feasible to produce trained professionals with a creative problem-solving attitude as well as the ability to foresee and model the outcomes of their professional actions by employing a systematic strategy during professional training. We now examine a person-oriented strategy as our next option [4].

One of the key elements in the interaction and improvement of the educational system is integration. One of the top concerns for raising the standard of vocational

education is the employment of integrative approaches in the training of specialists in the tourist industry under current circumstances. The employment of an integrated approach in professional training and professional activity is justified by the necessity to combine heterogeneous, mixed sectors of professional activity, interdisciplinary knowledge, skills, and capacities. Modern definitions of the integrative method include the integration of the individual with the future professional activity, or the sum of the person's competency, fundamental skills, knowledge, and abilities. Integration is achievable, according to V.V. Skotorenko and I.G. Mosyagin, if the research and study subjects have similar substance, are constructed on common patterns and broad theoretical concepts, employ the same research methodologies across disciplines, and have similar or common student activity methods [5].

It is really important to keep in mind that Western and Russian linguistics are currently being examined from the perspective of psycholinguistic research, which focuses primarily on issues related to producing and understanding speech, speech communication, as well as practical applications of the theory of speech activity. It is necessary to provide this knowledge to students of non-linguistic specializations as well, for this reason. In fact, learning a foreign language is viewed in the system of professional training of students as a way to develop the personality of the student, taking into account his or her motivations, interests, requirements, and abilities.

It should be noted that when examining the role of language and consciousness within the context of the professional mastery of language knowledge, skills, and abilities, modern processes of globalization, integration, and differentiation force researchers to take a different approach to many scientific theories and evolutionary processes that are occurring at this stage of society's development. There is a growing interest in a variety of linguistic and cultural phenomena that define the distinctiveness of specific racial and ethnic groups, picked out on the basis of shared values, and which affect how representatives of various corporate cultures interact. Subcultures, which comprise members of a single professional group and are tied together by shared interests in a variety of professional group theories, should be taken into account. This includes members of the subculture who both own and do not possess information on the subject [6].

The interaction between those connected to the business and the tourists is one of the most crucial elements of tourism. The act of exchanging information with another person is called communication, and it serves to transmit, receive, comprehend, and perceive information. Through both non-verbal parts of communication, such as glances and gestures, and verbal aspects of communication, such as language, which is the most natural connection between people, effective communication is crucial in making an impression on tourists. English has a significant impact on tourism because:

- instructions, signs, inscriptions are copied in English in numerous non-English speaking nations for ease of comprehension;
- seen as the common language of the 21st century;
- is the fourth most widely used mother tongue worldwide.
- is the official language that is most generally used;
- It is the primary language utilized in matters of state, business, tourism, and so forth.
- is a lingua franca or an international language; [7].

As a medium of communication and dissemination of the spiritual heritage of the nations of the studied language and peoples, a foreign language has taken precedence. Specialists in the tourism industry deal with communication issues on a daily basis, not only in their native tongue but also in a foreign tongue. Meetings with foreign partners, working as a guide-interpreter for foreign tourists, and being an animator in a foreign hotel all call for the employee to have a fair amount of language proficiency as well as knowledge of the culture and history of the nation whose representatives he is currently representing and momentary manager of tourism. Knowing the speech manners and customs used by business partners or tourists in their country fosters positive emotions during communication and leads to a deeper understanding, all of which are beneficial for a tourism manager's work results, boost his company's reputation, and ultimately increase enterprise profit.

This is why learning a foreign language should be one of the ways that professionals in the tourism industry study intercultural interactions and develop the necessary skills. To overcome the cultural barrier, which is much more perilous and unpleasant than the language barrier because cultural errors are typically perceived as being much more painfully than linguistic ones, tourism managers should take into account not only language training but also cultural and intercultural training. generally avoid saying goodbye and leave a bad impression [7].

Traveling abroad can increase one's personal investment in knowledge and increase the usefulness of learning a foreign language. Language-learning excursions that blend learning and fun have recently grown in popularity. Such journeys enhance language proficiency. Study abroad programs are primarily offered in nations where the national tongue is an international language. A personal approach is all that a language-training tour includes, and each tour is chosen based on the excursionist's age and level of foreign language skill. Since the majority of communicators worldwide speak English, we can draw the conclusion that English ability is crucial to success in the tourism industry in the present era.

In the context of the economy's trans nationalization, speaking English is a requirement for establishing a career. Additionally, learning a foreign language, especially English, develops clear pronunciation, tolerance, sociability, and tolerance for racial and socioeconomic diversity. Due to English's prominence as an international language, which, of course, makes it easier to communicate in any place in the globe, this language is taught and skill in it is required [8].

CONCLUSION

Therefore, in conclusion, it should be noted that the knowledge of foreign languages of tourism workers plays an important role in the tourism and hospitality industry today. It is very difficult to work in this field without knowing a foreign language. Therefore, every tourism enterprise manager should pay great attention to this.

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